

A Noble Cost Effective Distributed Electronic Health System for Patient Data Handling: Bangladesh Perspectives

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Abstract—Health system is one of the vital components for the people of any country. The use of electronic health in Bangladesh is very limited. As a result, health cost is increasing day by day and the poor people of Bangladesh could not bear the increased health cost. In this study, we are going to propose and develop a cost effective distributed electronic health system for patient data handling considering Bangladesh perspectives. By using this model, both patients and doctors will be connected through our developed system. We have used open source electronic health system, business process diagram and distributed characteristics of health system in this research. We have successfully shown from the result section that this model works as a distributed electronic health system. Our developed system is interoperable and cost effective which are the noble characteristics. Health data of patients are easily distributed and managed through the developed system. Finally, we can conclude that the developed system will change the current health system of Bangladesh and bring a new dimension for the healthcare sector.

Keywords- *Interoperable; business process diagram; electronic health system; electronic health record; directorate general of health service*

I. INTRODUCTION

A health system refers a number of health professionals providing health services to people individually or with the help of institutions and combination of various medical resources. At present, for the blessing of information and communication technology into electronic health system where health services can be provided and taken by electronic medium that is more accessible, secure and cost-effective. Most of the developed countries initiated distributed electronic health system to make the system more worthy. On the other hand, developing countries are also trying to introduce this kind of

distributed electronic health system. Very unfortunately, they are still struggling because of the complexity of the system.

For any nation, a well-organized health system is must which ensures proper health services to the people. As we know, healthy people are blessing for any nation, they are more productive and evaluated the economic growth for the country. Electronic health system plays a vital role for ensuring a well program health service for the people of developing countries. When people meet any medical issues, they can seek help from electronic health system. Like the developing countries, Bangladesh also needs electronic health system and it will be more effective if we introduce distributed electronic health system.

Medical data are increasing rapidly day by day and it is necessary to deal with large amounts of Electronic Health Record (EHR). For dealing with these problems, a hybrid approach that combines the advantages of static and dynamic approaches are generated [1]. Haridimos Kondylakis and other researchers worked on the implementation of a data management infrastructure for big health-care data in 2018. Authors introduced an effective and efficient method of patient data handling [2].

Bangladesh is a small country with huge number of populations. The ratio of population and doctor in Bangladesh is very low. The financial status of the major people of Bangladesh is very critical. It is very difficult to give healthcare to people in rural and remote communities of the developing world [3]. Health cost of the people is also very high. Maintaining a proper health system has become a great challenge for Bangladesh. As the health system of Bangladesh

is not proper to meet the needs of its people in comparison with other developed and developing countries.

TABLE I. POPULATION HEALTH WORKFORCE OF BANGLADESH

S.N	Description of the facilities	Ratio	Year
1	Physicians per 1000 people	0.581	2018
2	Nurses and Midwives per 1000 people	0.412	2018
3	Specialist surgical workforce per 1000 people	2.91	2018
4	Community Health worker per 1000 people	0.476	2012
5	Hospital beds per 1000 people	0.8	2015

Table 1 shows the current statistics of health worker with respect of the population in Bangladesh. From the figure, we can see that there are less numbers of doctors than patients, less numbers of well-trained medical professionals in Bangladesh. If we want to serve the medical treatment to huge number of patients, we need to develop an electronic health system in such a way so that we can minimize the health cost and manage health data efficiently.

According to the directorate general of health service (DGHS) of Bangladesh, health facilities are distributed in Bangladesh for the population of Bangladesh as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Health system structure of Bangladesh

Ward, Union and Upazila level hospitals of Bangladesh provides the primary health care facilities. District, divisional and national level hospitals of Bangladesh provides the secondary health care facilities to the people. Special health care facilities are given to the people have provided by the secondary level hospitals.

In order to ensure the health care facilities for the people of Bangladesh, government has taken different initiatives for the people though telemedicine service. Figure 2 shows a scenario of these types of arrangements in Union level.

Figure 2. Telemedicine services of Union level hospitals of Bangladesh

According to figure 2, government has provided laptop with camera and internet to the Union level hospitals. Local doctors register patients and get primary signs from them and send these to the expert doctors. Expert doctors communicate with the local patients through a video conferencing system. Based on the conversation and the provided data from the local doctors, expert doctors provide a medication plan and it is then delivered to the patients from the Union level hospital. This telemedicine service saves time and money for the local patients of Bangladesh.

Figure 3. Telemedicine services model through Mobile

The government of Bangladesh has also created 24 hours health-care facility though mobile as shown in figure 4. Through this model, people can talk directly with the doctors in 24 hours for emergency health service though mobile calls. This initiative enables patient to be connected with the doctors through mobile and they are getting a minimum emergency health service from a doctor.

Bangladesh government taken many initiatives for improving their health system using electronic health system and this system will be more effective if Bangladesh government introduce distributed electronic health system. Electronic health system provides us the facilities of managing health data efficiently. Patients sometime change their geographical positions for a variety of reasons. If they are unable to produce their health record in the changed position, they will have to do the health check-up again and their health cost increases. So, there is necessity to initiate some form of health system to meet these problems. Distributed electronic health system will create the path to overcome the challenges. This research proposes and implemented distributed electronic health system to offer most advanced health system for Bangladesh and also prelude for future.

This paper is organized into five sections. Section one presents the introduction of the research, section two highlights the literature review where recent related literatures were critically reviewed, section three depicts the materials and methods section, section four shows the results of the research and section five finally concludes with the conclusion section.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this section, we have reviewed some of the recently published literatures and conference papers with a view to find out the recent advancement on distributed electronic health system. Literature review helps us to address the current advancement, technology used, and future direction. The limitations are addressed and overcome in the proposed research.

Md. Rakibul Hoque, Md. Fahim Ahsan Mazmun and Yukun Bao describe and evaluate the current status of e-health in Bangladesh. In this paper, they also describe the initiatives taken by the government of Bangladesh in e-health system. Bangladesh government and private organizations have taken different initiatives on health system using ICT [5].

Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan conducted a survey on the telemedicine services in Bangladesh and they found that 66.23% doctors in hospital are not connected with telemedicine system. 94.80% doctors and 91.42% patients want to introduce this system. This paper proposed that telemedicine operating cost in the range of 201-300 tk. Author conducted the survey through questionnaires they made for local people, local doctors and expert doctors [6].

Tanvir Ahmed, Henry Lucas, Azfar Sadun Khan, Rubana Islam, Abbas Bhuiy and Mohammad Iqbal had explored 26 ehealth and mhealth initiatives in Bangladesh. The most initiatives are performed in private sector. The common initiatives include tele-consultation, prescription and referral [7].

Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman, Israt Jahan, Ahsin Abid, Mohtasim Bellah developed a portable telemedicine tool kit for remote diagnosis of patients which is low cost and easily accessible. Because of their tool kit and the developed system, a rural person does not need to travel to the urban area hospital. Their low cost portable tool kit can collect seven vital signs of patients through sensor. Their developed system is able to show the real time data of patients to the doctor [8].

A low cost security system for telemedicine service is developed by Toufik Ahmed, Uzzal Kumar Prodhon, Mohammad Zahidur Rahman and Israt Jahan considering the cost and efficient in performance. The system follows the recommendation of HL7 and FHIR also consider the HIPPA and NEHTA for security and privacy of a health system. In this paper they have included five sections where security measures are implemented. Bluetooth connection, Mobile Application user authentication, Mobile Application security, Sensor Data security, Server securities are applied in their system [9].

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Prodhon reviewed eight different models of patient data handling. They suggested distributed data can be an alternate choice for region-wise health data will be stored in the local database. This paper proposed Raspberry Pi based client model for the patient data handling [10].

Saroj Kanta Mishra, Indra Pratap Singh, Repu Daman Chand bring out the current status of telemedicine network in India and also visualize the future perspective. They describe the initiatives taken by the government of India, the state government and also some of private sectors. The government of India launched some pilot projects such as SAARC (South Asian Association of Regional Co-operation) telemedicine network, Pan-African e-network project [11].

Richard Wootton found that telemedicine brings clinical benefit in a cost effective way. In this paper, he reviewed the present evidence and also brought the need of telemedicine in future [12].

Niamat Ullah, Pervez Khan, Najnin Sultana and Kyung Sup Kwak describe the past and present health care system of Pakistan and also discuss about present telemedicine project taken by the government and private hospitals. In this paper, they propose a remote telemedicine system for rural area. They proposed a star networking central controlling model which is connected to the service center in rural area. According to their model, rural people can also take service from specialized doctor from urban areas and it's a store and forward base model [13].

In this research, Rashid L. Bashshur, Timothy G. Reardor and Gary W. Shannon describe the brief history of telemedicine from where telemedicine came out. Researcher added that, telemedicine service should be cost effective, accessible and ensure quality health service [14].

In this article, Shengnan Chen, Alice Cheng and Khanjan Mehta discuss about telemedicine business model. Researcher has chosen Alexander Osterwalder's "Business Model Canvas" which is composed of nine building blocks. Here they selected eight telemedicine ventures and divide the venture into two categories like developed and developing countries. The developed world mainly targets the organization and companies and on the other hand developing countries mainly target individual because of poor economical state [15].

Sapal Techkra, X.H. Wang, Robert S.H. Istepanian and Y.H. Song briefly described the mobile e-health. Mobile telecommunication technology is improved day by day and researcher explains it here with full description. To provide emergency treatment mobile telemedicine system need to implement [16].

IEEE 802.11 wireless standard to QoS (Quality of Service) support within wireless e-health services was investigated by PhD Anna Zvikhachevskaya, Prof. Garik Markarian and Dr.

Lyudmila Mihaylova. In this paper, they discussed about different types of handoff in digital system like hard handoff, soft handoff and softer handoff. Handoff is a complex function which introduces the uninterrupted communication of an ongoing call. This approach was used to save life of critical patients [17].

From the literature review section, we have found that there are scopes to introduce distributed electronic health system for Bangladesh. The introduction of this approach is very limited and if we want to deliver a cost effective efficient health service to the people of Bangladesh we should introduce distributed electronic health system.

III. METATERIALS AND METHODS

To develop a successful distributed electronic health system for Bangladesh, three modules were introduced in this research. The modules are based on patients, doctors and administrator activities where each module interconnected to each other. The distributed electronic health system has been developed following a mesh connectivity system where each health system will be distributed to different servers and each server will be connected to each other so that they can pass data frequently. Following figure 4 is the developed mesh connectivity diagram of the system. The developed system shows only the connectivity with the four divisions. We can easily extend the developed system to more divisions as needed.

Figure 4. Block diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

Figure 5 shows a Business Process Diagram (BPD) diagram of distributed electronic health system has been developed. Based on the figure 4, there are three main processes in the BPD diagram. These are patient module, doctor module and administrator module. The system activities start from the registration of patients. As soon as, a patient gets registered and apply for an appointment to any specific doctors, the request will be forwarded to the doctor. Patients will get proper treatment according their report and health information. The administrator will validate all kinds of data and update any data if necessary. Further details of the module are discussed in the following section.

Figure 5. BPD diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

A. Patient's Module

In order to get any service from the developed distributed electronic health system, patients will have to get registered first. A unique ID is generated to any patient. Registered patients will have to login to the electronic health system and apply for an appointment to any doctor they want. After getting the appointment, the patient will have to provide some of the other health information as per demand of the patient and communicate with the doctor if needed. The patient and doctor must validate their information through the system. Patients can get the prescription from the system and they will make the payment of the service through this module.

B. Doctor's Module

Doctors are one of the most vital components of the developed system. Patients get connected with the doctor through the system. In order to give telemedicine service to the patients, doctors will have to register first. When any patient is registered with the doctor, registered doctor will be notified for new appointments through the system. Doctor can approve or decline the appointment. After successful log-in with the system, doctors can get the history of patients by using unique patient ID. After communicate with the patient, doctor prepares a medication plan and delivers the medication plan to the patients.

C. Administrator Module

In order to run and maintain the system, administrator will validate all the necessary information of the patient and doctor for registration and provide unique ID and password. Administrator manages the system and also updates the patient

and the doctor profile if necessary. Administrator is responsible for smooth functioning of the system.

D. Augmented Activity Diagram of Developed Model

Figure 6 show agents interaction of the developed distributed electronic health system. There are three agents in the model such as patient, doctor and admin. Every agent is interacted with each other according to the goal of the research. The activities of patient and doctor are presented in the figure 6. Patients have to register with their valid information and login to the system. Then request for appointment and get notify for service. After that process the payment, communicate with doctor and received the prescription. Doctor also registers with their valid information and login to the system. Approved appointment and received patient history. Then review patients and generate prescription for the patient. Distributed electronic health system admin manage and maintain the whole system for proper functioning.

Figure 6. Augmented activity diagram of developed distributed electronic health system

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We have implemented our system as per the design of the block diagram and BPD diagram. We have successfully used an open source electronic health system for our research work and connected our health systems according to design. We have customized the health system according to our need which is suitable for Bangladesh. We have distributed our health system and successfully connected the health module and get the health service. We have also checked for the case of geographical change patients and got correct results. This approach removes the dependency of the centralized health system and offers the benefits of distributed system. If any health system fails, it is easy to deliver the health service to

the patients of the failed node. As a result, we can continue our health services for any rural people of Bangladesh.

Now, we are going to present some of the section-wise output here for the acceptance of the system. At first, users need to register in the distributed electronic health system with their valid information. Figure 7 shows the registration of user as output. The users may be patient or doctor.

Figure 7. Registration status of new users of the developed system

After registering into the system, the user gets a username and password for log-in into the system. Every user can enter the system with user login password. Figure 8 shows the log-in status of user from the developed system.

Figure 8. Login window of the user from the system

User interface of the developed system is shown in figure 9. From this interface, every service is initiated from window. Patients, doctors, payment, report, maintenance and other services are initiated from here.

Figure 9. User interface of the developed system

Both doctors and patients are registered into the system first to get or deliver healthcare service. Our system can successfully register the user as shown in the figure 10. Doctors can use their patients detail from this list and prescribe medicine for them. Patients can also select category-

wise doctors from the doctors list and get medical treatment from the respective doctors.

Figure 10. Doctors and patients list from the developed system

Most of the doctors want to know the patients history for the proper treatment of the patients. In traditional system, patients need to carry health record manually or patient's record is kept in the server of a particular hospital. In Bangladesh health data are not interoperable among the hospitals. We have overcome this problem through the use of open source distributed electronic health system. Now, patient's health history is now interoperable with other health system and can be used from any node as shown in the figure 11.

Figure 11. Interoperable patients health record from the developed system

When a patient is registered into the system, the administrator assigns a specific doctor for the treatment of the patient. After completing the registration system, the doctor can see the appointment status for his patients and patient is also get information from the system about the appointment confirmation. Figure 12 shows the appointment status of the patient with the doctor.

Figure 12. Appointment request status of a patient to a specific doctor

After successful appointment, consultation is made by using our developed system. Here both patient and doctor interacts each other for the treatment of the patient. Administrator helps both parties for the successful completion of the consultation. Figure 13 shows the patient's document and final report.

Figure 13. Patients documents and report section

We have made our system distributed in nature. As a result, we can access our system from any node any time. System failure of any node would not hamper to the whole health system. If any patient changes their geographical position, he/she can get the medical service from the changed position easily. Patient's history of one node can be easily accessed from other node. We can easily find the patients information through our system. Doctors can easily get the patients diagnostic information from our system. So, they can provide quality and efficient care to the patients. Figure 14 shows the accessibility status from any device.

Figure 14. Accessibility status of the system from anywhere

After successful consultation is completed, doctors will give a medication plan to the patient. The medication plan is printed from the service delivery point. System administrator will assist to the patient for getting the prescription. Figure 15 shows the prescription generated from our developed system.

Figure 15. Prescription of the patients from the system

We have also included the billing section in our model. By using our system, each patient can easily get the financial status easily and can pay the bill. Collected amount is automatically distributed to the concerned parties. Figure 16 shows the billing section from the developed system.

Figure 16. Patients billing system from the system

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have successfully designed and developed a noble distributed electronic health system for patient data handling. In this study, we have used four nodes as a distributed environment where our customized electronic health system is running. According to the design of our system, we have registered patients in one node and he/she is able to get his medical service from any other node. We have made our design in a cost effective way so that this model is effective for the rural general people of any country of the world including Bangladesh. We have the health system which is more flexible and efficient. Billing, medication plan, accessibility, inter-operability and usefulness are the key characteristics of the developed health system. Finally, we can say that our developed distributed electronic health system will play a great role for the advancement of the health system of Bangladesh.

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